

UNIVERSITY OF WEST BOHEMIA

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

There is no law in the Czech Republic that deals with gender-based violence or sexual harassment specifically in higher education institutions and research organisations. There are several national policies that mention sexual harassment, but all of them devote only a few sentences to the issue, usually in the form of recommendations for the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports to deal with this phenomenon.

The number of institutions that have taken concrete steps to deal with this issue has increased more substantially just very recently (especially in the past two years). These steps were prompted by instruments introduced to tackle this issue as part of various national and international research and higher education policies. An important factor was the introduction of financial support for higher education institutions (HEIs) by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports to motivate HEIs to set up their strategic management in accordance with the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for Recruitment and apply for the HR Excellence in Research award. Many Czech HEIs used this support, and it led many of them to initiate the first steps to promote gender equality (including introducing measures to prevent and eliminate gender-based violence).

Other developments at the national level also served as incentives for institutions to take action. “Dealing with sexual harassment” was included as a recommended activity in the 2019 Implementation Plan of the Ministry of Education’s Long-Term Plan for Educational and Scientific Activities, Research, Development and Innovation, and Artistic and Other Creative Activities in Higher Education 2016–2020. The financial scheme linked to this plan, the Centralised Development Programme, also offered support for activities that focus on promoting gender equality (including fighting sexual harassment). Universities are also regularly reminded of the need to take action in this area by a requirement imposed by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports to report annually on how they deal with sexual harassment (a requirement in place since 2018). In addition, in 2020 sexual harassment was for the first time included (as part of the gender equality indicator) in the Methodology for Evaluating Research Organisations and Research, Development and Innovation.

These instruments are applied primarily in the higher education sector. There are no similar stimuli for other Research Performing Organisations (RPOs). For this reason, the problem of gender-based violence has so far been addressed primarily in the university environment but less in terms of concrete institutional policies.

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The only policy document that the University of West Bohemia (UWB) has that deals with gender-based violence is the Code of Conduct of the University of West Bohemia (Etický kodex Západočeské univerzity v Plzni) which is a more general document, not specifically dedicated to GBV.

The document defines the ethical principles and values to which UWB adheres. It is binding for all UWB staff and students. It covers sexual harassment, coercion, and gender harassment. GBV is defined as unacceptable behaviour. As written in the document, it is the responsibility of each individual to report such behaviour when confronted with it. It is the Ethics Committee that monitors compliance with the ethical standards set out in this code. The Ethics Committee deals with suggestions from UWB staff and students concerning alleged violations of ethical standards at UWB. Members of the Ethics Committee are appointed by the Rector. Several members are ad hoc members. At least one ad hoc member for each of the student-related suggestions being discussed is a student. The Committee must be gender-balanced.

URL

- › Code of Conduct of the University of West Bohemia:
<https://www.zcu.cz/rest/cm/document/workspace://SpacesStore/cea0de95-d79b-4483-9772-c0a2051a3fd5;1.0/content>

Entry into force: 2019.

TRAINING

The Ethics Committee members receive training on all the topics covered in the Code of Conduct.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

Not specified.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The document covers sexual and gender-based harassment.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: One of the Ps is covered by the document, that is, policy since the document sets out a procedure for reporting and investigating cases of GBV.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Intersectionality addressed

No

Specific vulnerable groups

Not defined

Target groups

The document addresses academic staff, non-academic staff, students and also participants in lifelong learning courses.

Bystanders addressed: Yes. The Code of Conduct includes the following statements (p. 4): ‘It is the responsibility of each individual to report such behaviour, when confronted with it, to a senior employee or the Ethics Committee of UWB. (...) If individuals encounter unethical behaviour in their surroundings, they must not tolerate it: neither out of loyalty nor for their own benefit. They must always strive to remedy such behaviour and do everything possible to prevent such behaviour in the future. Employees report suspected unethical behaviour to their senior employees or to the UWB Ethics Committee. Students report alleged unethical behaviour to the UWB Ethics Committee.

Role of perpetrators addressed: No.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: Not specified.

Monitoring: No.

Evaluation: No.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

The Code of Conduct of the University of West Bohemia specifies the procedure at the student vs staff level.

The policy defines: who to contact.

Who to contact: Employees report suspected unethical behaviour to a senior employee or to the UWB Ethics Committee. Students report alleged unethical behaviour to the UWB Ethics Committee.

Additional information

In addition to the above-mentioned documents, the University of West Bohemia adopted a Gender Equality Plan¹ which sets as one of its priority areas prevention of GBV. It proposes several measures, one of them is the revision of the Code of Conduct as well as services associated with it (e.g. establishing an ethics line as a support tool for the prevention of negative phenomena).

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Jana Dvořáčková in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c

¹ For more information see <https://www.zcu.cz/rest/cmris/document/workspace://SpacesStore/aacb3acc-2f85-4da8-858f-e8dc8a43d09b;1.0/content>

